

**List of conference contributions for Swen Brands, Instituto de Física de Cantabria (CISC-UC),
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- Rush W, Lora JM, Skinner CB, Shields CA, Brands S, Guan B, Mattingly KS, McClenny EE, Mundhenk BD, Nellikkattil AB, O'Brien TA, Ramos AM, Reid K, Shearer E, Waliser DE, Wille J (2023) Atmospheric River Detection Under Changing Mean-State Climate and Seasonality: ARTMIP Tier 2 Single-Forcing Paleoclimate Experiments, A53M-2440, Poster
- Brands S (2022) An exhaustive global climate model performance assessment based on Lamb weather types. EMS Annual Meeting 2022, EMS2022-206, <https://doi.org/10.5194/ems2022-206>, Solicited oral
- Brands S, Fernández-Granja J, Fernández J, Bedía J, Casanueva A, Taboada JJ (2022) Performance of the CMIP6 global climate models over the Iberian Peninsula and relationships with the simulated climate system complexity. 12º Congreso Internacional AEC. Oral
- Lemus-Canovas, M and Brands, S (2020): Assessing several downscaling methods for daily minimum and maximum temperature in a mountainous area. Are we able to statistically simulate a warmer climate in the Pyrenees? EGU General Assembly 2020, EGU2020-11389, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu2020-11389>, 2020
- Brands S (2017) Which teleconnections are robust to internal atmospheric variability ? EMS Annual Meeting 2017, EMS2017-764, oral
- Manzanas R, Brands S, San-Martín D, Gutiérrez JM (2014) Sensitivity of Statistical Downscaling Techniques to Reanalysis Choice and Implications for Regional Climate Change Scenarios. 2014 AGU Fall Meeting. Oral
- Eiras J, Brands S, Miguez-Macho G (2014) Extreme precipitation events over the Iberian Atlantic Margin: The role of atmospheric rivers. 2014 AGU Fall Meeting. Poster
- Brands S, Herrera S, Fernández J, Gutiérrez JM (2013) How well do CMIP5 Earth System Models simulate present climate conditions? A performance comparison for selected CORDEX domains. International Conference on Regional Climate - CORDEX 2013. Oral.
- Brands S, Herrera S, Fernández J, Gutiérrez JM (2012) How well do CMIP5 Earth System Models simulate present climate conditions in Europe and Africa? 8º Congreso Internacional AEC. Poster
- Brands S, Herrera S, Fernández J, Gutiérrez J.M. (2012) A new source of seasonal predictability for the winter climate in Spain. 8º Congreso Internacional AEC. Oral
- Brands S, Manzanas R, Gutiérrez JM, Cohen J (2012) Seasonal Predictability of Wintertime Precipitation in Europe Using the Snow Advance Index. 12th Annual Meeting of the European Meteorological Society (EMS) and the 9th European Conference on Applied Climatology (ECAC). Oral
- Manzanas R, Gutiérrez JM, San-Martín D, Brands S, Herrera S (2012) Assessing the robustness of statistical downscaling techniques for their application under climate change conditions. 12th

Annual Meeting of the European Meteorological Society (EMS) and the 9th European Conference on Applied Climatology (ECAC). Oral

Brands S, Taboada JJ, Cofiño AS, Schneider C, Sauter T (2010) Statistical downscaling of daily temperatures in northwestern Spain from an ensemble of AR4-GCMs. European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2010. Poster